

COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH IN THE ASPECT OF THE INTERACTIVE METHOD OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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In didactics, a teaching method is defined as an organized method for achieving educational and developmental goals. Currently, there is no single definition of the concept of "teaching method." Modern didactics offers numerous classifications of teaching methods, for example: 1) by source of knowledge: verbal, visual, and practical (I. Perovsky, N.M. Verzilin, Ya. Golant); 2) by primary didactic goals: knowledge acquisition, development of skills and abilities, application, reinforcement, and verification (M.A. Danilov, B.P. Esipov), etc.

When selecting teaching methods for developing research competencies, we used a competency-based approach as a basis, which demonstrates the need to use active and interactive teaching methods in the educational process. Interactive teaching of foreign languages is particularly relevant today. Interactive learning is a special form of organizing the educational process, the essence of which lies in the joint activity of students in mastering educational material, solving common but meaningful problems for each student, and in the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and methods of activity.

The strategy of interactive learning is the organization by the teacher of the educational process using a specific system of methods, techniques, and techniques based on:

- subject-subject relationships between the teacher and student (parity);
- multilateral communication;
- student knowledge construction;
- the use of self-assessment and feedback;
- student activity [2].

Interactive teaching methods, according to A.N. Ioffe, "...are all types of activity that require a creative approach to the material and provide the conditions for each student to develop their potential" [3].

The use of interactive methods allows for the creation of conditions for:

- setting goals and objectives that require the search for and analysis of various solutions;
- selecting various methods of activity to achieve a result;
- development of communication skills and abilities; reflection on work completed;
- development of important social skills such as speed and flexibility;
- thinking when making decisions, a critical approach to problems;
- respect for the opinions of others, the ability to work effectively in a group, a team, and more quickly adapt to new situations, a new team, and changing conditions.

Interactive teaching methods often enable the achievement of higher-order goals in the educational process.

Interactive teaching methods include:

The research method, according to N.S. Romantseva (6, p. 58), aims to update existing knowledge and skills, as well as to acquire new ones;

a personally and significantly significant learning outcome. The teacher and student become full partners.

This method facilitates the transition from instruction to self-education.

The implementation of the research method addresses the following objectives: 1) developing students' research skills and abilities through work with popular science, educational, and reference

literature; 2) generalizing and systematizing knowledge across various subjects and on the topic of their research; 3) developing a culture of scientific thinking; 4) teaching public speaking skills.

The project-based method is based on the idea of developing students' cognitive skills, creative initiative, independent thinking, problem-solving, information navigation, and the ability to predict and evaluate the results of their own activities. The project-based method focuses on students' independent activity over a specific period of time. According to E.S. Polat, this method is applicable when there is a truly significant problem (practical, scientific, creative, or real-life) whose solution requires research.

While research aims to reach the truth, project-based work is aimed at a comprehensive study of the problem and entails obtaining a practical result (a video, album, poster, newspaper article, instruction manual, etc.).

Educational discussions are a form of cognitive activity in which participants in the educational process purposefully exchange their opinions, ideas, and judgments on the educational problem under discussion. They are increasingly used in the practical work of teachers in professional educational institutions at various levels of training. Discussions are useful for conducting problem-based educational conferences and discussing complex, cross-curricular issues.

Discussions help develop communicative skills (communication skills, formulating and asking questions, defending one's point of view, etc.), analytical and synthesis skills, problem identification skills, and more.

We assign an important role to didactic games (business and role-playing games, blitz games, etc.) in developing research competencies.

Student draw.

Each student receives a token. If a child receives a blue token, they will play the role of a sick person. The back of the token contains the illness (have a headache, have a sore throat, have an earache, have sore eyes, have a high fever, have a toothache, have a stomachache, feel exhausted).

Students who receive green tokens will play the roles of doctors (a Physician, an Oculist, a Dentist, a Surgeon, an Ear-Throat-Nose Doctor). The back of the tokens indicates which doctors they will be. One student will be assigned the role of a receptionist (a nurse).

Years of Independence in Education

Kazakhstan has undergone fundamental changes. One of the priority tasks is the implementation of the "Trinity of Languages" project—a goal born from the dream of a bright future for the nation. To achieve this, a prerequisite is the development of communicative competence not only in one's native language but also in foreign languages. Mastering English opens the door to the global information space. There are numerous methods for teaching English. Moreover, new ones are regularly developed, so every teacher can not only choose but also develop the most appropriate teaching method. At this time, when the state demands that we cultivate active, independent, and enterprising citizens who will develop our country in the future, updates to the new educational curriculum are being introduced. The updated educational curriculum in our country aims to improve teachers' pedagogical skills in the context of an updated curriculum and the introduction of a criteria-based assessment system. One of the important goals of the updated program is "Teach – Learn"—lifelong learning, which will contribute to the development of a new, competitive, comprehensively developed, and functionally literate individual.

The goal of the communicative method is to teach people to communicate in real life.

This method differs from others in that the fictional texts and texts far removed from real life that students study in other methods are replaced by dialogues from everyday life. Students act them out in a way that provokes conversation, that is, motivates each other.

The communicative method differs from other existing methods in that students using this method don't know how the lesson will end, who will answer a particular question, or how—it all depends on the situation. Each lesson features new topics for discussion and new types of exercises. This is done to ensure that students are well-rounded and at the same time prevent them from becoming bored with learning.

During lessons, students primarily communicate, but time is also devoted to writing and reading. Teachers focus solely on listening, guiding students' activities, and assigning exercises. When students begin to actively discuss something, the teacher merely observes.

	Activity of teacher	Activity of pupils
Lesson		
Let's remember		
Phonetic tasks +	Let's learn the poem: Can you play with your dog? Can you sleep on the mat? I can play with my dog, I can sleep in my bed	Repeat after teacher Answer the questions:
Training	Have you got a pet? Is this a dog? Can it play ball?	
Repeat after teacher	Are you sleeping (twice)? Brother John (twice) Morning bells are ringing Ding-ding dong (twice). Working with cards Match the sentences and their translation: 1.Can he play hockey? 2. Is he a sportsman? 3. They can play badminton. a) They can play badminton. b) Is he an athlete? c) Can he play hockey? Are you sleeping (twice)? Brother John (twice) Morning bells are ringing Ding-ding dong (twice). Working with cards Match the sentences and their translation: 1.Can he play hockey? 2. Is he a sportsman? 3. They can play badminton. a) They can play badminton. b) Is he an athlete?	Learn
Work with cards		Do the task

Proper use of modern information technology in elementary school contributes to:

- enhancing cognitive activity and improving students' academic performance;
- achieving learning goals through modern electronic learning materials designed for use in elementary school lessons;
- developing self-study and self-monitoring skills in primary school students; improving learning comfort;
- reducing students' learning difficulties;
- increasing the activity and initiative of primary school students in the classroom; developing information-based thinking; and developing information and communication competence;
- developing computer skills in primary school students while adhering to safety regulations.

The use of interactive methods in education allows for a differentiated learning process tailored to students' individual needs, enables creative teachers to expand the range of methods for presenting educational information, allows for flexible management of the educational process, and is socially significant and relevant. Computer programs help create a variety of visual illustrations and audio accompaniment, which facilitates the better implementation of the principle of visual aids in teaching.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Лазарев В. С., Конопина Н. В. Деятельностный подход к формированию содержания педагогического образования /2022.
2. В. Конопина // 2023 Педагогика № 3.
3. Languages: 1971-81. - Strasbourg. Council of Europe Press, 1981
4. Communication in the modern languages classroom/By Joe Sheils. Strasbourg: Council of Europe Press, 1993
5. Threshold Level 1990. - Strasbourg: Council of Europe Press, 1991
6. Асмолов, А. Г. Системно-деятельностный подход к разработке стандартов нового поколения / А. Г. Асмолов. – М.: Просвещение, 2023.
7. Мудрик А. В. Введение в социальную педагогику: учебное пособие для студентов. М.: Институт практической психологии, 1997